

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

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Prepared by members of the Pacific Invasives Partnership and representatives of the Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs)

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The Pacific Invasives Partnership (PIP) is the invasive species working group of the Pacific Island Round Table (PIRT) for Conservation of Nature. PIP members working on invasive species issues are people from regional organizations, regional programmes, international conservation NGOs, research institutions and agencies of the New Zealand, US, and Australian governments.

Mission: To promote coordinated planning and assistance to meet the invasive species management needs of the Pacific Island Countries and Territories.

Strategy: PIP is dedicated to ensuring the successful implementation of the Guidelines for Invasive Species Management in the Pacific. It facilitates coordination and cooperation between agencies working on invasive species issues in the region and assists Pacific Island Countries and Territories in addressing their invasive species priorities.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

Contents

Executive Summary	2
History and Context	3
Scope of the Plan	5
Goal	5
Objectives and Actions	5
Objective 1: Prevent the entry and establishment of invasive ants into the Pacific region and prevent their subsequent spread to new locations within the region	5
Objective 2: Implement an efficient and effective early detection and rapid response system for invasive ants that operates at regional, jurisdictional and island scales	6
Objective 3: Mitigate the impacts of priority invasive ants already present in the region	7
Objective 4: Increase the level of public and political awareness and support of invasive ant biosecurity	7
Objective 5: Enhance local and regional capacity for invasive ant biosecurity and management	8
Objective 6: Implement an active research program that provides practical improvements in detection and management of invasive ants	8
Objective 7: Establish a centralised support role to coordinate and assist PICTs to implement the Plan, with an exit strategy that enables local capacity to continue to deliver the Plan Objectives	9
Appendix 1 (Provided separately): Status and Needs for Implementation	9
References	9

Executive Summary

The tropical Pacific Islands are made up of 22 countries, territories, and the U.S. State of Hawai'i, within three sub-regions of Micronesia, Melanesia, and Polynesia. Combined, the Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs) are populated by around 14 million people with a land area of around 600,000 square kilometres. The region's large maritime size, relatively small economies, and complex socio-political structures combine to present many unique challenges, particularly when confronted with climate change and ensuring ecosystem resilience, food security, cultural resources, quality of life, and long-term sustainable development. Unequivocally, the wellbeing of Pacific Island communities and the ecosystems that support them are inextricably linked.

Invasive species cost the global economy approximately 5% of GDP each year⁽¹⁾. Invasive ants are one group of organisms that cause substantial impacts to ecosystems, economies and human health. The predominantly insular biotas of the Pacific Islands are un-adapted to invasive ants^(2,3), resulting in invasive ant impacts often being far greater than on mainlands. These impacts threaten not only complex island ecosystems and endemic biota, but the livelihoods and wellbeing of island communities. Climate change interactions with invasive ants are also envisaged to reduce the climate resilience and food security of subsistence economies.

Some invasive ants such as the Yellow Crazy Ant (*Anoplolepis gracilipes*) are widespread in the Pacific. Their impacts include complete ecological "melt-down" such as that observed on Christmas Island⁽⁴⁾ resulting in large changes to the ecosystems. On Johnston Atoll, seabirds are unable to nest

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

and rear young due to continual bites and predation of hatchlings⁽⁵⁾. In other locations, episodic population explosions of Yellow Crazy Ant over-run entire islands, causing massive nuisance to people and animals^(6,7). The Little Fire Ant (*Wasmannia auropunctata*) is spreading rapidly through the region. This species forms massive three-dimensional supercolonies that blanket the ground layer and the forest canopy⁽⁸⁾. They sting residents, cause blindness in domestic and wild animals, impede agricultural activities, and reduce forest and agricultural productivity⁽⁹⁾. The Red Imported Fire Ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) and the Tawny Crazy Ant (*Nylanderia fulva*), while not yet present in the region, both have the potential to cause devastating impacts to Pacific islands. The Red Imported Fire Ant (RIFA) is now present in several countries in the Pacific Rim. Some of these countries are significant trading partners with Pacific nations and territories. Even the rigorous biosecurity systems of Australia and New Zealand have been unable to exclude RIFA^(10,11). The potential cost of RIFA impacts alone is estimated to be almost 1% of PICT GDP, with 61% of those costs being due to impacts on crops and livestock, and the remainder including the likes of medical and tourism¹².

Preventing invasive species incursions is far more cost effective than management¹³. In 2004, the Invasive Species Specialist Group of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature published the Pacific Ant Prevention Plan (PAPP)⁽¹⁴⁾ in response to regional concerns with the potential entry and proliferation of invasive ants such as RIFA. Since then, these concerns have increased, as have the spread and impacts of invasive ants, and there is now a regional desire to also manage the impacts of existing invasive ant species. This document, The Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific (BPIAP), is a logical evolution of the PAPP.

This updated Plan details the actions required to best improve biosecurity and management of invasive ants in the Pacific at local, country and regional levels. This plan has been jointly developed by representatives of many PICTs and other members of the Pacific Invasives Partnership from New Zealand, Australia and the USA, and was formally completed at the first Pacific Ecological Security Congress held in Palau, 3-5 October 2022.

History and Context

The risk of spread of invasive ants was highlighted in early 2001 when RIFA was discovered in both Australia and New Zealand. The New Zealand incursion was localized (one large nest); treated, and triggered a broad surveillance effort that achieved eradication from the country⁽¹⁵⁾. Australia also initiated an eradication attempt and despite eradicating six incursions to date, including one covering over 8000ha⁽¹⁶⁻¹⁸⁾, the largest incursion covering the entirety of Brisbane still persists after an investment of almost 500 million dollars⁽¹⁹⁾. These incursions demonstrated that invasive ants were being moved by commerce, were capable of arriving and establishing within countries with world-class biosecurity systems, and can be very costly to eradicate. Smaller PICTs do not have the same levels of resources to apply to biosecurity. Meetings in the Cook Islands (2002 Global Biodiversity Forum) and Hawai'i (2002 Global Invasive Species Program workshop) highlighted these issues to policy makers in the region.

The IUCN Invasive Species Specialist Group convened a workshop in September 2003 in Auckland with the aim of developing a regional plan to combat the threats of new introductions and to mitigate the impacts of existing invasive ant species in the region. This meeting resulted in the development of the Pacific Ant Prevention Plan (PAPP 2004) that encompassed RIFA and other exotic invasive ants with documented negative impacts. The PAPP was presented and endorsed at a subsequent meeting of the Pacific Plant Protection Organization (PPPO) and the Pacific Community (SPC) agreed to be the lead agency in implementing the plan.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

Although some elements of the PAPP were addressed in subsequent years, these efforts were largely uncoordinated and often very localised. Additionally, with time the invasive ant species landscape in the Pacific region changed considerably. The Little Fire Ant emerged as the most devastating ant species in the region. In 2003, this species was confined to the Solomon Islands, New Caledonia, the outer islands of Vanuatu, and had just been detected on Hawai'i Island and Tahiti. Since that time to the present (2021) it has spread to Papua New Guinea, French Polynesia (Moorea, Rurutu islands), Vanuatu (Espiritu Santo and Efate), other Hawaiian islands (Oahu, Kauai, and Maui), Australia, Guam, Yap (Federated States of Micronesia), and American Samoa.

Little fire ants are an agricultural pest. They farm mealybugs and scale insects which cause disease to plants (photo shows mealybugs on cocoa). They also sting workers when they harvest products (Photo: Cas Vanderwoude)

Little fire ant stings on a child's leg, Wewak, Papua New Guinea (Photo: Cas Vanderwoude)

New incursions of RIFA continue to be detected: two more incursions in New Zealand have been eradicated^(13,20), and as of early 2021 there are currently three incursions undergoing eradication in Australia⁽¹⁹⁾, two of which arrived in the last two years. Impacts from infestations of Yellow Crazy Ant continue especially on Tokelau, Tuvalu, Christmas Island, Hawai'i and elsewhere. Singapore Ants (*Trichomyrmex destructor*) continue to spread in Palau. As a result of the increasing need for ant biosecurity in the Pacific, in 2017 the PAPP was revised and renamed the Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific (BPIAP).

Red tailed tropicbird swarmed by yellow crazy ants (Photo: Stefan Kropidlowski, USFWS)

Singapore ant infested walls causing fire hazards. (Photo: Ben Hoffmann, CSIRO, Australia)

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

The 2022 Pacific Ecological Security Conference (PESC) was the catalyst for again revising the BPIAP. The PESC was an international Pacific Island invasive species summit attended by Pacific Island country experts and partners that notably involved the endorsement of multiple new or updated Strategic Action Plans focused on invasive species management, including this BPIAP. It was envisaged that the Plans would build consensus on best management practices and enhance overall coordination between PICTs and research partners, as well as identifying gaps and needs. The expected outcome of the PESC and this BPIAP are subsequent coordinating activities that will take a “whole of Pacific” approach to addressing critical concerns about invasive species spread and management.

Scope of the Plan

The biosecurity plan is intended for use by all island nations, states, and jurisdictions within the tropical Pacific region: American Samoa, Australia, Cook Islands, Federated States of Micronesia (FSM), Fiji, French Polynesia, Guam, Hawai`i, Kiribati, Marshall Islands, Nauru, New Caledonia, Niue, Northern Mariana Islands (CNMI), New Zealand, Palau, Papua New Guinea (PNG), Pitcairn Islands, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tokelau, Tonga, Tuvalu, Vanuatu, and Wallis and Futuna.

Goal

To prevent invasive ant species with economic, environmental or social impacts, from entering and establishing in the tropical Pacific region and to mitigate the impacts of existing invasive ant species.

Objectives and Actions

Objective 1: Prevent the entry and establishment of invasive ants into the Pacific region and prevent their subsequent spread to new locations within the region

Preventing any invasive species from arriving in new locations is far more cost effective than attempting eradication post arrival, or incurring management and impact costs for perpetuity. Actions of Objective 1 aim to minimise the likelihood of entry of new invasive ant species into the Pacific, or further spread both among and within PICTs.

Legislation:

- a) Identify existing legislation, policy and standards that support regulatory activities.
- b) Determine whether existing legislation, policy and/or standards are sufficient to support regulatory activities.
- c) Ensure the measures under this Plan fit within existing legislation or are considered during development of new legislation.
- d) Where needed, re-draft or write new legislation, policies or standards that are required to effectively prevent entry or spread of invasive ants.
- e) Strengthen inter-island biosecurity within PICTs.

Risk analyses:

- a) Identify the most appropriate international risk assessment framework and adapt this framework for use in the region.
- b) Conduct or update Pest Risk Analyses for ant species of regional significance for the Pacific (PICT and regional-level analyses).
- c) Conduct Pathway Analyses of goods into and/or through the Pacific to predict the entry of invasive ant species into the Pacific and/or subsequent spread among and/or within PICTs.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

- d) Review known and potential economic, environmental and social impacts of new invasive ant species entering the global trade network.
- e) Engage trade and support agencies within each jurisdiction and make risk assessments available to them, encourage multilateral negotiators to consider these at regional level.

Operations:

- a) Advocate for Pacific-wide implementation of the Sea Container Hygiene System (SCHS).
- b) Manage high-risk pathways.
- c) Develop best-practice operational systems that are appropriate for jurisdictions within the Pacific region.
- d) Assess current capacity including funding for implementation of best practice operational systems for each jurisdiction and support actions that increase jurisdictional capacity.
- e) Review and audit operational systems at regular intervals.

Objective 2: Implement an efficient and effective early detection and rapid response system for invasive ants that operates at regional, jurisdictional and island scales

Eradication is often only possible when a species is at the very early stages of establishment. The quicker a species is found, the fewer the places it has dispersed to, the smaller the area it is found within, and the quicker that effective treatments can be conducted to achieve eradication. Actions of Objective 2 aim to prepare PICTs to detect and respond to new ant incursions as quickly and effectively as possible.

Early detection:

- a) Use risk analyses to identify surveillance sites with different risk levels (i.e. arrival entry points, unloading facilities, waste management facilities).
- b) Establish regular targeted surveillance at key (high risk and other sentinel) sites.
- c) Collate baseline information on invasive ants currently present in PICTs.
- d) Develop Standard Operating Procedures for surveillance.
- e) Develop mechanisms to review and modify an overall surveillance program.
- f) Review the status of collections of preserved specimens of globally-significant ant species to aid rapid species identifications, and update or develop them as required.

Incursion preparedness:

- a) Identify gaps in capacity and resources, and investigate ways to fill them.
- b) Develop communication and data sharing protocols and mechanisms.
- c) Define and obtain agreement for national and regional reporting requirements and protocols for new invasive ant detections.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

- d) Identify resources and availability of equipment and supplies for immediate use in the event of an emergency response.
- e) Develop a network of people with expertise, both within jurisdictions and the region, for Emergency Responses, and invasive ant biology.
- f) Ensure sufficient funding is available to conduct an emergency response.

Emergency response procedures:

- a) Develop Emergency Response Plans for each PICT for priority invasive ant species.
- b) Conduct regular incursion simulations to test incursion response plans and support systems.
- c) Review and modify standard operating procedures as new methodologies become available.

Objective 3: Mitigate the impacts of priority invasive ants already present in the region

If an exotic species cannot be eradicated from a jurisdiction, there are still actions that could be taken in some circumstances to reduce the species' negative impacts, or even eradicate it from smaller areas of significance. Actions of Objective 3 aim to determine which species could be subject to management, and in which contexts, and encourage such actions to be taken.

A prioritized list of species targeted for ongoing management:

- a) Quantify the economic, social, environmental, and agricultural impacts of any invasive ant species present.
- b) Compile or update a prioritized list of existing invasive ant species at regional, jurisdictional, and island levels.
- c) Develop management plans for high-priority species, potentially at regional, jurisdictional, island and even site-level.

Availability of equipment and supplies:

- a) Ensure a supply of equipment and supplies to manage existing species is available to jurisdictions.
- b) Conduct strategic ant management.
- c) Foster the establishment of a regional network of practitioners with ant management skills.
- d) Develop strong links between practitioners and the applied research community.
- e) Conduct eradications on any spatial scale if feasible, or practical mitigation programs where significant economic, social, or environmental outcomes can be achieved.

Objective 4: Increase the level of public and political awareness and support of invasive ant biosecurity

It is often the public that first find new incursions when they report nuisance or unusual ant activity. Public support of eradication measures is critical for eradication success, just as much as public compliance with movement controls helps prevent spread of invasive ant species. The greater the public awareness of the issues of invasive ants and their many roles for invasive ant biosecurity, the greater the ability to detect new incursions early, the greater the chance to achieve eradication, and the lower the chance of accidental spread of established species to new locations. Actions of Objective 4 aim to increase public awareness and support for invasive ant biosecurity and management.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

Public and political awareness:

- a) Maintain and enhance the common pool of resource material available for regional/national use in the Pacific Invasive Ant Toolkit (<https://piat.org.nz>) (e.g. photos, information, fact sheets, contact lists, school curriculum suggestions).
- b) Identify links with other successful complementary invasive species awareness programs
- c) Develop a communication plan, including identification of key people (spokesperson) within each PICT, resource requirements, and potential sources.
- d) Ensure awareness materials are developed to most effectively achieve the goal at regional, national, and local levels.
- e) Conduct awareness programs.

Objective 5: Enhance local and regional capacity for invasive ant biosecurity and management

Most biosecurity activities, especially conducting eradications, involve specialised tasks. Such tasks are conducted at higher standards when people are trained in the conduct of those tasks. Activities of Objective 5 aim to provide training opportunities for people involved in the many tasks associated with invasive ant biosecurity.

Capacity building:

- a) Identify training and capability gaps and develop learning packages to fill these gaps.
- b) Foster taxonomic personnel and provide opportunities for professional development and interaction with colleagues worldwide.
- c) Develop and implement training packages for people involved in all aspects of ant management.
- d) Provide professional development opportunities for practitioners including collaboration interactions with colleagues worldwide.

Objective 6: Implement an active research program that provides practical improvements in detection and management of invasive ants

There are many science opportunities that would enhance invasive ant biosecurity and eradications. Actions for Objective 6 aim to facilitate the conduct and dissemination of such science opportunities. The highest priority research opportunities that would benefit the PICTs are listed in the research priorities checklist.

Research:

- a) Establish a network of researchers and research agencies that focus on invasive ant management.
- b) Conduct the research listed in the research priorities checklist.
- c) Identify availability, gaps, and sources of funding for research.
- d) Establish clear dissemination pathways for research results.
- e) Encourage the development of emerging researchers within the region and foster their professional development.
- f) Facilitate annual publication of research agenda and deliverables.
- g) Convene regular workshops to disseminate results and prioritize research needs that include practitioners, extension personnel, and policy staff as a mechanism for information dissemination and priority setting.

Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

Research priorities checklist:

- a) The development of new target-specific genomic baits that reduce non-target impacts (RNAi, gene drive).
- b) The advancement of technologies for rapid ant identification (ID app, lateral flow immuno assays, field-based CRISPR), detection (biosensors), including genomics.
- c) The advancement of baiting technologies, specifically autonomous UAV technology and delivery systems for treating complex and difficult landscapes.
- d) The development of a new website much larger than the Pacific Invasive Ant Key (<http://idtools.org/id/ants/pia/>) hosting a pacific-wide taxonomic database specifically for on-line diagnostics, potentially accompanied by a hard-copy version.
- e) Further development of species-group keys (like those on antwiki) of important groups that contain exotic and horizon species.
- f) The development of genomic methods such as the HTS-amplicon (metabarcoding) method for mass biosecurity assessments that can be used for both proactive post-border surveillance and monitoring within management programs.
- g) Taxonomy that resolves the species-level identity of problematic species-groups or genera (e.g. *Ochetellus*, *Iridomyrmex*, *Hypoponera*, *Monomorium*, *Pheidole*, *Nylanderia*).
- h) Conduct pathway analyses of key commodities to predict the entry of invasive ant species into the Pacific and subsequent secondary and tertiary spread within and among PICTs.

Objective 7: Establish a centralised support role to coordinate and assist PICTs to implement the Plan, with an exit strategy that enables local capacity to continue to deliver the Plan Objectives

Actions to improve ant biosecurity in the Pacific can be conducted at numerous levels, from locally to regionally. As such, there are many biosecurity actions that can be taken individually by each PICT, but there are also some that would require inter-PICT coordination. A local and independent coordinating body/agency is best placed to provide support and coordination for PICTs to implement the plan, especially to the point where individual PICTs are fully self-sufficient to conduct effective invasive ant biosecurity.

Coordination and assistance:

- a) Undertake a process to determine to agree on a regional coordinating body/agency.
- b) Obtain funding for the support role.
- c) Develop an exit strategy.

Appendix 1 (Provided separately): Status and Needs for Implementation

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Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

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Appendix 1: Summary of Status and Needs for Implementing the Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific

Background

Before, during, and immediately after the Pacific Ecological Security Conference in Palau (3-5 October 2022), attendees and invitees of all PICTs were requested to complete a survey of their completion status, as well as their expertise and financial assistance needs, relative to the highest-priority Actions drafted within the updated version of the Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific. Responses were received from 14 PICTs and the results are summarised here in three tables. The results are just as applicable for individual PICTs to identify their priority Actions to progress ant biosecurity, as well as external parties to identify how they can assist PICTs to achieve such progress. Note that results are summarised for the three regions of the Pacific, but individual PICT responses are available upon request. Those PICTs that have not yet provided input will be further requested to provide responses, to obtain the most comprehensive dataset possible.

Brief summary

Table 1 – Completion of Actions

- Two thirds of responses indicated that the highest-priority Actions needed to be conducted within PICTs, with only one third of responses stating that Actions were either underway or completed.
- No PICTs had Emergency Response Plans for any invasive ant species, with the exception of Hawaii, which had a single plan for RIFA.
- There were very few completed Pest Risk Analyses or Pathway Analyses.
- Only one third of responses indicated that some form of pro-active surveillance was being conducted.
- Most (64%) PICTs stated that they currently don't have professional development opportunities for people responsible for invasive ant biosecurity.
- Approximately half of the PICTs had no Awareness Activities for invasive ants.

Table 2 – Expert assistance needed?

- 82% of responses indicated that expert assistance was needed to conduct Actions.

Table 3 – External financial assistance needed?

- 97% of responses indicated that external financial assistance was needed to conduct Actions.

Table 1. Number of PICTs in the three Pacific regions relative to their completion of highest priority Actions for invasive ant biosecurity. Columns highlighted yellow indicate where there is high-priority opportunity to progress invasive ant biosecurity.

Activity	Micronesia			Melanesia			Polynesia		
	Done	Doing	Needed	Done	Doing	Needed	Done	Doing	Needed
Establish targeted surveillance	1	1	3	0	1	2	1	1	3
Develop Standard Operating Procedures for surveillance	1	0	4	0	1	2	1	0	4
Identify gaps in capacity, capability and resources	1	0	4	0	1	2	0	1	4
Develop communication and data sharing protocols	1	0	4	0	1	2	0	1	4
Establish a network of people with expertise, for Emergency Responses, and invasive ant biology	1	0	4	0	1	2	1	0	4
Develop Emergency Response Plans for priority invasive ant species	0	0	5	0	0	3	0	0	4
Conduct awareness programs	0	2	1	0	1	2	2	0	3
Provide professional development opportunities	0	2	1	0	0	3	1	1	3
Determine whether existing legislation, policy and/or standards are sufficient to support regulatory activities	1	0	5	1	2	0	3	2	0
Ensure the measures under this Plan fit within existing legislation	1	0	5	0	2	1	1	4	0
Conduct or update Pest Risk Analyses for key ant species	0	0	6	0	0	3	1	1	3
Conduct pathway analyses	0	0	3	1	0	2	0	2	3

Table 2. Number of PICTs in the three Pacific regions relative to their need for personnel assistance to complete highest priority Actions for invasive ant biosecurity. Columns highlighted yellow indicate where there is high-priority opportunity to progress invasive ant biosecurity.

	Micronesia		Melanesia		Polynesia	
	Can do alone	Experienced help wanted	Can do alone	Experienced help wanted	Can do alone	Experienced help wanted
Establish targeted surveillance	2	3	0	3	1	4
Develop Standard Operating Procedures for surveillance	2	3	0	3	1	4
Identify gaps in capacity, capability and resources	1	4	0	3	1	4
Develop communication and data sharing protocols	1	4	0	2	0	5
Establish a network of people with expertise, for Emergency Responses, and invasive ant biology	1	4	1	2	1	4
Develop Emergency Response Plans for priority invasive ant species	1	4	0	3	0	5
Conduct awareness programs	2	1	2	1	2	3
Provide professional development opportunities	1	2	0	3	2	3
Determine whether existing legislation, policy and/or standards are sufficient to support regulatory activities	0	6	0	3	2	3
Ensure the measures under this Plan fit within existing legislation	0	6	0	3	0	5
Conduct or update Pest Risk Analyses for key ant species	0	6	0	3	1	4
Conduct pathway analyses	0	3	0	3	2	3

Table 3. Number of PICTs in the three Pacific regions relative to their need for financial assistance to complete highest priority Actions for invasive ant biosecurity. Columns highlighted yellow indicate where there is high-priority opportunity to progress invasive ant biosecurity.

	Micronesia		Melanesia		Polynesia	
	No funding needed	External funding needed	No funding needed	External funding needed	No funding needed	External funding needed
Establish targeted surveillance	1	3	0	3	0	4
Develop Standard Operating Procedures for surveillance	0	4	0	3	0	4
Identify gaps in capacity, capability and resources	0	4	0	3	0	4
Develop communication and data sharing protocols	0	4	0	3	0	4
Establish a network of people with expertise, for Emergency Responses, and invasive ant biology	0	4	0	3	0	4
Develop Emergency Response Plans for priority invasive ant species	0	4	0	3	0	4
Conduct awareness programs	0	2	0	3	0	3
Provide professional development opportunities	0	2	0	3	0	3
Determine whether existing legislation, policy and/or standards are sufficient to support regulatory activities	0	6	0	3	1	4
Ensure the measures under this Plan fit within existing legislation	0	6	0	3	0	5
Conduct or update Pest Risk Analyses for key ant species	0	6	0	3	1	4
Conduct pathway analyses	1	1	0	2	0	3